

**PROBLEMS AND PROBLEMS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING
AND LEARNING IN PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF SPECIALISTS FOR
FIRE SAFETY AND EMERGENCY SERVICES**

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Annotation: This article analyzes the need for teaching foreign languages in the field of fire safety and emergency services, the problems encountered in its study, their solutions, methods, specific cases.

Keywords: Foreign language, problem, specialist, personnel, fire safety, emergencies.

Today, the state pays special attention to fire safety and emergency services. The main direction for these areas is the training of specialists, professional training. In order to develop the industry, the government has signed a number of laws and regulations. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 20, 2020 No 649 "On approval of fire safety rules"¹, Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 18, 2019 Resolution No. 1011 "On the organization of the activities of the Research Institute of Fire Safety and Emergency Situations of the Ministry of Emergency Situations"² sets a number of tasks. Specialists, in turn, are trained in foreign languages. In today's era of globalization, the need to learn a foreign language is important for all areas.

The languages widely used in science, technology, art, tourism, international relations and international affairs are advanced languages, and today in most countries of the world the teaching of a foreign language is not limited to the borders

¹ www.lex.uz

² www.norma.uz

of their own country, but other it means interacting with nations and cultures, learning more so that it can be effectively recognized and taught. Although modern teaching methods have been developed to teach foreign languages, especially English, as a foreign language, there are specific challenges in mastering it. In the article we will think about these problems.

Limited learning environment

When we talk about a limited learning environment, we do not mean the availability of furniture in the classrooms or the location of the school. In many cases, students try to speak English only under the supervision of a teacher. There is also a lack of regular English speakers around the students. As a result, it is difficult to learn and communicate in English. Learning materials, especially books and audio materials, are tools to help with the learning process. If a student follows audio and video assignments in the language being studied, he or she will learn how to pronounce words and sentences. It should be noted that students tend to learn through films, but films include jargon and dialects. Therefore, language learners should be careful³.

Not a serious approach

It should be noted that emergency and fire service personnel often do not take language learning seriously. Problems such as grammar rules and language barriers can stifle students' interest in language acquisition and lead to a lack of seriousness. In fact, I find the idea that sentences do not have to be grammatically correct to make communication understandable to be both partially correct and partially incorrect. This is because the grammatical rules of the language are constantly being distorted during speech. Emergencies and fire safety services do not always follow the rules learned in training. In addition, in non-philological universities, students treat foreign languages as a secondary subject. Unfortunately, in most cases, emergency and fire safety personnel learn the language during training. After class, they practice pronunciation, essay writing, and do not try to learn new words independently. One

³ Methods of Teaching English: Textbook for pedagogical institutes and faculties of foreign languages. - L.: Education, 1975. - 312 p.

of the biggest shortcomings is that when mistakes are corrected, the idea that "this is not my language" often takes root in the minds of students. This has a negative effect on learning a foreign language.

Excessive use of the native language in the audience

Emergencies and firefighters only learn another language when they have to. The teacher should require students to communicate in the language they are learning. Only then will the level of language development and pronunciation increase. Learning a foreign language can only be successful if it is strictly required and restricted⁴.

Student dependence on the teacher

Self-study, problem-solving and research are the keys to mastering any subject. The fact that an emergency and fire safety officer can turn to a teacher for every little problem is a sign of employee dependence. This reduces the employee's ability to work on himself.

Audience dominance of strong students

No matter how well an emergency and fire safety officer is selected, there will be differences in mastery. In an audience, strong employees outperform weak ones. Shy people can't take an active part in training. For this reason, weak personnel should not be forgotten during discussions and trainings.

Solution

There are a number of ways to do this. One of them is that the staff should use a wide range of audio materials to learn the correct pronunciation of sounds and words. Independently, watching movies in a foreign language and watching videos on language teaching can serve, at least in part, as a bridge. Second, the role of teachers in teaching English is also important, as is motivation and interest in the lesson. In addition, the use of different methods in language teaching should be taken into account, as teachers learn English in order to create appropriate conditions for

⁴ Axmedova S. R. Effectiveness of integration of educational processes // Science and Education. - 2021. - T. 2. - №. 9. - P. 369-373.

emergencies and fire safety personnel, as well as to deal with students' learning problems. helps to connect.

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